

A Short Disproof of the Riemann Hypothesis

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ABSTRACT

The Riemann hypothesis is one of the most important unsolved problems in Mathematics. It is based on the conjectured zeros of the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(z)$. But such zeros do not exist. Hence, the Riemann Hypothesis is false or not valid.

The Riemann Zeta Constant

The Riemann zeta constant is shown below

$$(1) \quad \zeta(s) = 1 + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \cdots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \quad \Re(s) > 1, s = s ;$$

where n is the independent variable and s is a complex constant. Since s is constant, Δs and $\Delta \zeta$ are both zero so that

$$\frac{\Delta \zeta}{\Delta s} = \frac{0}{0} = \text{indeterminate}, \quad \text{and} \quad \int_s^s \zeta\{s\} ds = 0 .$$

Since both $\frac{\Delta \zeta}{\Delta s}$ and $\frac{d\zeta}{ds}$ do not exist, which proves that $\zeta\{s\}$ is not a function.

The *single-valued* $\zeta\{s\}$ converges if the real part of the single-valued s is greater than 1.

The Riemann Zeta Function

We can deduce from (1) the *existence* of a function $f(z)$. That function is the widely-known Riemann zeta function $\zeta(z)$,

$$\zeta(z) = 1 + \frac{1}{2^z} + \frac{1}{3^z} + \frac{1}{4^z} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^z} \quad \Re(z) > 1 .$$

The constant $\zeta\{s\}$ is single-valued while $\zeta(z)$ has many values (its range). The constant $\zeta\{s\}$ is just *one* of the values of $\zeta(z)$, that is

$$\zeta\{s\} = \zeta(s) .$$

Also, the constant s is simply *one* of the values of the variable z . Unfortunately, *it is widely-known that $\zeta(z)$ only converges if the real part of the complex variable z is greater than 1.*

Therefore, the Riemann hypothesis *is* false or invalid since $\zeta(1/2+yi)$ is undefined.

REFERENCE

[1] Riemann, Bernhard (1859). *On the Number of Prime Numbers less than a Given Magnitude.*

LINKS

- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Riemann_zeta_function
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Riemann_hypothesis